

Original Research

Collaborative Networks and Furniture Manufacturing SMEs Performance in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania: The Mediating Role of Customer Loyalty

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of collaborative network dimensions on furniture manufacturing SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam, focusing on customer loyalty as a mediator. Employing a quantitative, correlational design, data were collected through structured questionnaires from a stratified randomly selected sample of 350 furniture manufacturing SMEs owners or managers. The data were analysed using Covariance-Based Structural Equation modelling. The findings revealed that, in presence of customer loyalty as a mediator, collaborative relationships with suppliers and competitors had significant positive effects on furniture manufacturing SMEs performance. Although firm's relationships with customers had a positive association with performance, its direct effect was not statistically significant. Hence, customer loyalty was found to fully mediate the effect of firm's relationships with customers on furniture manufacturing SMEs performance and partially mediating the effects of collaborative relationships with suppliers and competitors. This study extends the traditional market orientation framework by incorporating collaborative networks as a substitute for inter-functional coordination in driving SMEs performance through customer loyalty as a mediator. Furniture manufacturing SMEs should form alliances for joint procurement, engage in knowledge exchange forums, and form joint marketing consortia to access quality inputs, reduce costs, drive innovation, and expand market reach. To translate relationship with customers into loyalty and improved performance, the enterprises should ensure consistent product quality, timely delivery, and responsive after-sales services. The Ministry of Industry and Trade, should support inter-firm networking via clustering programmes and supplier development initiatives.

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Introduction

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a pivotal role in global socioeconomic development. They make up approximately 90% of businesses worldwide and contribute significantly to employment and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (United Nations, 2023). In sub-Saharan Africa, SMEs constitute the majority of enterprises, contributing nearly 50% of the region's GDP and offering approximately 80% of employment opportunities (Cooper, 2023; Shariff, 2023). In Tanzania, SMEs are similarly vital, comprising over 90% of all enterprises and contributing around 35% to the national GDP and 40% to employment (Tonya & Samwel, 2024).

Within the SMEs landscape, furniture manufacturing stands out as a critical component of an industrial base. The furniture sector accounts for about 4% of global manufacturing output and provides roughly 3% of jobs worldwide (Koridze, 2022). According to the International Labour Organization (2022), the furniture industry employs about 50 million people worldwide. The sector's global market is experiencing steady growth driven by urbanisation, population growth, rising incomes and consumer demand for home and office furnishings. The global furniture market value reached USD 568.60 billion in 2024 and is projected to exhibit a compound annual growth rate of 5.65%, growing from USD 597.71 billion in 2025 to USD 878.14 billion by 2032 (Fortune Business Insights, 2025).

In Tanzania, furniture manufacturing holds considerable promise for job creation, local value addition, and export potential (Nkwabi, 2020). Furniture Manufacturing SMEs (FM-SMEs) alone account for nearly 6% of the manufacturing workforce and are strategically positioned to serve both the domestic and international markets (Guadagno *et al.*, 2019). The sector is projected to reach a market value of USD 606.03 million by 2025, with an estimated annual growth rate of 1.37% between 2025 and 2029 (Statista, 2024), largely fuelled by urbanisation and the expansion of the middle class.

To unlock this potential, the Tanzanian government has implemented a range of strategic initiatives in line with Vision 2025 and the Third Five-Year National Development Plan (2021/22–2025/26). These include the creation of wood furniture production hubs (Expogroup, 2025), reforms to procurement policies to prioritise local sourcing, and tax incentives on imported raw materials (URT, 2021). Additionally, the Small Industries Development Organisation (SIDO) offers technical support to enhance productivity, while a 35% tariff on imported furniture under the East African Community framework aims to boost local competitiveness (Textor, 2025).

Despite their promising growth potential and governmental efforts, FM-SMEs continue to face challenges that hinder their performance. High start-up failure rates, estimated to be between 60% and 70% within the first three years, reflect several constraints, such as technological inadequacy, outdated production techniques, and

limited access to quality raw materials and finance (Mwagike, 2024; Israel, 2022; Kumburu & Kessy, 2021). Intense competition from imported furniture, often perceived as superior in design and more affordable, further exacerbates this situation (Kumburu & Kessy, 2021). The subsector is also largely fragmented and informal, hindering access to credit, government incentives, and formal market opportunities, along with a general lack of managerial and marketing capabilities to understand and respond to consumer preferences and market trends (Mwagike, 2024).

To address persistent performance challenges, FM-SMEs need to adopt strategic orientations to enhance their performance (Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020a; Guadagno *et al.*, 2019). Particular attention is increasingly being paid to market orientation as a prerequisite for firms to adapt and survive in today's competitive business environment. Market orientation refers to a firm's ability to generate, disseminate, and act on market intelligence to deliver value to customers (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990). Empirical studies affirm that businesses with strong market orientation consistently outperform the less market-oriented peers (Jummai, 2023; Nikmah *et al.*, 2020).

Traditionally, market orientation has been built on three pillars: customer orientation, competitor orientation, and inter-functional coordination (Narver & Slater, 1990). However, in the context of SMEs, inter-functional coordination is considered less relevant because of SMEs' simple structures, informality, and resource constraints (Mamman, 2021; Bamfo & Kraa, 2019). As an alternative, scholars suggest collaborative networks with external actors as a more practical coordination mechanism (Lu *et al.*, 2024).

Collaborative networks refer to formal or informal partnerships with external stakeholders, including suppliers, customers, and even coopetitors to enhance competitive position and business capabilities. Such networks enhance firms' competitiveness and superior performance by facilitating knowledge exchange, shared problem-solving, and access to resources (Ganeshu *et al.*, 2024; Kweka & Fadhili, 2020). This strategic approach is particularly relevant for SMEs as the majority are plagued by low performance, especially in developing countries (Ismail, 2024; Kweka & Fadhili, 2020). Nonetheless, effective strategic orientations alone are insufficient unless a firm can build and sustain a stable customer base, which is largely a result of customer loyalty (LOY) (Amoah, 2024; Rajagukguk *et al.*, 2024). Defined as the extent to which customers consistently choose and remain committed to a firm and its products, LOY has long been recognised as a key driver of firm performance (Albarq, 2023). However, there is limited empirical evidence on how collaborative networks affect firm performance through LOY. This study addresses this gap by examining the relationship between collaborative networks and firm performance in the context of FM-SMEs in Dar es Salaam, with a focus on the mediating role of LOY. It contributes to SMEs literature by positioning collaborative networks as a viable substitute for inter-functional coordination, while also providing empirical evidence on how such networks, through LOY, enhance SMEs performance.

Foundational Theory

This study was grounded in Network Theory and Relationship Marketing Theory (RMT). Network Theory posits that firms are embedded in webs of inter-organisational relationships that influence their strategic behaviour and performance outcomes. As an extension of Social Capital Theory, Network Theory was notably advanced by Granovetter (1985), who introduced the concept of embeddedness, and by Burt (1992), who emphasised the value of structural holes as sources of competitive advantage through non-redundant ties. From a network perspective, a firm's success is largely influenced by its external connections with key stakeholders such as suppliers, customers, peer firms, and regulatory bodies, rather than being determined in isolation.

Engaging in collaborative relationships provides firms with access to complementary resources, capabilities, and market insights that lie beyond their internal capabilities. Collaborative networks foster trust, social capital, and legitimacy, enabling information exchange and reducing transaction costs, thereby contributing to enhanced performance. For SMEs, especially those in resource-constrained settings, networks serve as critical enablers to access knowledge, materials, distribution systems, and market intelligence. By leveraging cooperative ties with suppliers, peer firms, and customers, Tanzanian FM-SMEs can overcome typical limitations, such as insufficient capital, outdated technology, and limited market reach.

Nonetheless, while Network Theory explains how external relationships benefit firms, it falls short of explaining the mediating role of LOY. To address this gap, this study integrates Relationship Marketing Theory (RMT). As pioneered by Berry (1983) and further expanded by Morgan and Hunt (1994), RMT emphasises building and maintaining long-term customer relationships based on trust, commitment, and value creation, which are central to LOY. Within this framework, LOY serves as a mediating mechanism through which a firm's networks may translate into enhanced performance. Supporting this view, Ismail (2023) establishes that LOY significantly mediates the positive impact of customer-focused orientation on SMEs performance in Tanzania. Thus, market-oriented practices most effectively improve performance when cultivating loyalty.

Hypotheses Development

Collaborative networks, including partnerships with suppliers, peer enterprises, and customers, are increasingly recognised as strategic pathways for enhancing firm performance (Jean, 2024). These networks allow businesses to overcome internal resource constraints, drive innovation, and effectively respond to market changes. At the same time, LOY is widely recognised as a key driver of business success by not only generating repeat businesses but also lowering marketing costs and fuelling growth through positive word-of-mouth (Obafemi *et al.*, 2023). Hence, the interplay between collaborative networks and LOY is deemed critical for enhancing firm performance (Nguyen Thi & Nguyen Thi Thu, 2022).

Collaborative relationships with suppliers, customer loyalty, and SMEs performance

Collaborative Relationship with Suppliers (CRS) involves cooperation with suppliers in areas such as information sharing, supply chain management, and innovation (Stekelorum *et al.*, 2022). Through CRS, a firm can secure more reliable inputs, reduce costs, and improve production efficiency and product quality (Liu *et al.*, 2024; Celikyay *et al.*, 2023; Gebisa, 2023; Mulyana & Wasitowati, 2021). Prabhu *et al.* (2024) revealed that strategic collaboration with suppliers promotes operational agility, which directly enhances the performance of manufacturing SMEs in India. Similarly, Israel (2025) found that CRS enables Tanzanian SMEs to access new technologies, exchange knowledge, and collaboratively develop innovative solutions. Uwamahoro *et al.* (2024) found that CRS significantly improved operational performance of manufacturing SMEs in Rwanda.

However, scholars and industry experts have cautioned that CRS is not always a guaranteed path to success. The effectiveness of these relationships depends on several factors, including external market conditions, the level of trust between collaborating entities, and the dynamics of bargaining power. In a study of Chinese SMEs, Zhang *et al.* (2025) found that heavy dependence on a few key suppliers negatively affected profitability and did not show a significant correlation with asset growth. Similarly, Brito *et al.* (2014) found that only certain collaborative behaviours with suppliers translate into performance gains, whereas others may be neutral or even detrimental. In their study of packaging manufacturers, Brito *et al.* (2014) found that information-sharing and fair use of power in supplier relationships improved financial outcomes, whereas excessive flexibility or joint problem-solving efforts had no benefit or negative effects. Thus, the impact of CRS can vary widely depending on how collaboration is managed and the context in which it occurs.

Beyond its direct effects on performance, CRS is theorised to indirectly influence performance through LOY. The logic is that, when SMEs collaborate closely with suppliers, they can ensure better product quality, timely delivery, and flexibility in meeting customer needs. Improved quality and reliability from the supply side lead to higher customer satisfaction, which in turn fosters greater loyalty. For instance, a study in Vietnam's electronics sector established that robust supplier–manufacturer collaboration enhanced a firm's competitive advantage and increased customer and loyalty (Nguyen Thi & Nguyen Thi Thu, 2022). However, empirical research that explicitly examines the mediating effect of LOY on the relationship between CRS and SMEs performance remains limited. To address this gap, it was posited that CRS not only drives performance directly but also contributes to building a loyal customer base that enhances performance. Accordingly, it was hypothesised:

H₁: CRS is positively associated with FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

H₂: CRS positively affects LOY.

H₃: LOY mediates the effect of CRS on FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

Collaborative relationships with coepetitors, customer loyalty, and SMEs performance

In recent years, coepetition has gained significant attention as an effective strategy for SMEs (Feela, 2020). It involves collaborating with other firms of a similar scale, including competitors or firms in related industries, to achieve mutual benefits. Network theory explains this by pointing out that sharing complementary assets and knowledge with peers helps firms overcome resource constraints and build competitive capabilities that translate into better financial and market performances (Worimegbe *et al.*, 2022). For instance, in the furniture sector, small workshops might band together to collectively purchase raw materials at bulk discounts, share expensive equipment, or jointly market their products. Such peer networking allows small manufacturers to pool resources, share knowledge, coordinate actions, generate economies of scale, and jointly tackle market challenges that a single firm cannot address.

The direct impact of coepetitor collaboration on firm performance has been a subject of growing empirical inquiry, yielding mixed results. Crick (2022) found that in New Zealand wineries, a higher degree of coepetition leads to greater customer satisfaction and improved market performance. The study suggests that by partnering with peer firms, SMEs can access new resources, markets, and innovations, thereby achieving performance gains that would be difficult to attain independently. Another recent study by Liu *et al.* (2024) on digital healthcare ventures in China confirmed that coepetition had a positive effect on venture growth performance. Through coepetitive ties, SMEs can undertake larger projects or innovate more effectively than they can individually, leading to higher sales growth and profitability.

Nevertheless, scholars perceive coepetition as a “double-edged sword” that delivers benefits but also potential downsides (Bimmermann *et al.*, 2024). A study by Bimmermann *et al.* (2024) on the “dark side” of inter-firm coepetition found that if competitive tension dominates the alliance, customer outcomes may suffer. Excessive rivalry among cooperating SMEs can erode trust and coordination, undermining service quality or innovation consistency. Similarly, Crick (2022) reported that in highly turbulent markets, simple coepetition agreements showed no significant impact on SME performance, suggesting that the effectiveness of coepetition is context dependent.

Beyond direct performance gains, Collaborative Relationships with Competitors (CRC) can indirectly benefit performance by enhancing the value delivered to customers, thereby building loyalty. When rival firms work together, customers may benefit from combined strengths, such as wider product variety or improved reliability, which in turn fosters greater LOY toward the participating SMEs (Worimegbe *et al.*, 2022). Crick (2022) provides evidence along these lines, showing that coepetition was linked to higher SMEs performance. This suggests that cooperative behaviour can increase customer trust and loyalty to the network of firms, as customers see that their needs are prioritised over individual firms’ rivalry. In a collaborative network, if one enterprise cannot fulfil a custom order, it could partner with neighbouring SMEs to meet the demand, rather than letting the customer go unmet.

However, Crick (2022) warns that overly aggressive competitive behaviour can disrupt this effect. If firms remain too antagonistic, the fruits of collaboration cannot be realized and customers may see little difference. Moreover, direct studies on coopetition-induced loyalty in SMEs remain scarce. It is plausible that in contexts such as the furniture manufacturing sector, coopetition could improve product variety and quality, or reduce costs, which could enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. However, empirical confirmation is required. Building on these insights, it was hypothesised that:

H4: CRC has a direct positive effect on FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

H5: CRC positively influences LOY.

H6: LOY mediates the effect of CRC on FM-SMEs performance.

Relationship of firms with customers, customer loyalty, and SMEs performance

Developing strong relationships with customers (RWC) is a cornerstone of SMEs success, and its performance implications are well-documented. Ismail (2023) provides direct evidence in the African SMEs context, indicating that maintaining RWC significantly increases LOY, which in turn, boosts firm performance. Likewise, Obafemi *et al.* (2023) established that SMEs investing in RWC often see direct performance gains such as higher profitability, sales growth, and market share. Moreover, engaging customers in product development or improvement can spur innovation and ensure that products meet market preferences, further contributing to firm performance.

The debate in the current literature is not whether this link exists between customer relationship efforts and SMEs performance via LOY but how strongly it translates into performance. Some scholars argue that the cost of maintaining a very high relationship intensity must be balanced against benefits, especially for small firms with limited resources. However, empirical evidence consistently underscores that customer relationships yield loyalty, which, in turn yields performance. A recent multi-industry study noted that firms prioritising customer satisfaction and loyalty achieved superior performance relative to their competitors (Ismail, 2023). This finding reinforces the idea that a customer-oriented strategy is crucial for SMEs to excel. In light of these findings, it was expected that in the context of FM-SMEs, RWC leads to greater LOY and better firm performance. Therefore, this study hypothesised that:

H7: RWC has a positive direct effect on FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

H8: RWC positively affects LOY.

H9: LOY mediates the effect of RWC on FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

Customer loyalty and SMEs performance

The theoretical foundation linking loyalty to performance stems from RMT which views loyalty as an intangible asset that yields a competitive advantage. Empirical evidence strongly corroborates this theoretical claim. For instance, Obafemi *et al.* (2023) found that loyalty contributes to increased profitability, business growth, and operational

efficiency, whereas Ismail (2023) established that firms with loyal customers consistently experience superior sales and overall performance. The key reason for this relationship is the economics of retention. Acquiring new customers is typically far more expensive than retaining existing ones. Loyal customers often buy more over time, which increases their lifetime value to the firm. They also serve as brand advocates, promoting the firm through positive word-of-mouth, thereby attracting new customers at little to no marketing costs.

However, emerging perspectives have begun to challenge the assumption that relational factors such as trust and personalized engagement are sufficient to build and sustain loyalty, particularly in contexts where product offerings are commoditised or markets are highly price-sensitive. In such settings, consumers may prioritise tangible performance indicators such as product durability, design, value for money, or pricing over interpersonal rapport. For instance, Amoah (2024) found that even strong customer relationships may not translate into loyalty unless they are supported by consistent product quality and functional value. This insight is especially relevant in emerging economies like Tanzania, where limited purchasing power makes price and quality the dominant drivers of loyalty.

Thus, while loyalty remains a key strategic asset, SMEs must recognise that, in certain contexts, relational engagement must be complemented by competitive product and service performance to secure long-term customer commitment. In this study, it was hypothesised that:

H₁₀: LOY positively affects FM-SMEs performance in Dar es Salaam.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework presented in Figure 1 illustrates the three dimensions of collaborative networks (CRS, CRC, and RWC) as independent constructs, with each influencing the dependent construct (FM-SMEs performance). The framework includes direct paths from each independent variable to FM-SMEs performance, corresponding to H₁, H₄, and H₇. Each independent variable is linked to LOY (the mediating construct), representing H₂, H₅, and H₈. A path from LOY to FM-SMEs performance is included, corresponding to H₁₀. The mediation hypotheses H₃, H₆, and H₉ are represented in the framework by indirect routes from collaboration variables to performance through LOY.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Research Methods

Research Approach and Population of Interest

This study adopted a quantitative, correlational research design to examine the hypothesised relationships. A correlational design was considered suitable because there was no manipulation of the variables, which is in line with Gawali's (2023) recommendations. The study was carried out in Dar es Salaam Region, as it hosts the highest concentration of FM-SMEs and serves as Tanzania's commercial hub (Kumburu *et al.*, 2019). A substantial number of local producers and imported furniture provide a distinctive strategic context for investigating how FM-SMEs in this region can manage competitive pressure and leverage LOY to enhance their market position.

Sampling

The study employed a dual stratified random sampling method using district and business size as the stratification criteria. The sampling frame was based on a list of 1,062 FM-SMEs identified in the 2015 Industrial Production Survey conducted by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in collaboration with the Ministry of Industry and Trade (National Bureau of Statistics, 2018). Although this survey is a decade old, it remains the most recent and comprehensive official source available for capturing the structural distribution of manufacturing establishments in mainland Tanzania. The reported district-level distribution was as follows: Kigamboni (53), Ubungo (156), Kinondoni (203), Ilala (223), and Temeke (427).

While the Industrial Production Census might have served as an alternative source, it was last conducted in 2013, and a new round is currently underway. In the absence of more current data, reliance on the 2015 survey for stratification is methodologically justified. This approach aligns with recommended practices in contexts where updated frames are unavailable, especially within fragmented and semi-informal sectors like FM-SMEs (Mohadjer & Choudhry, 2001; Verma, 1999). To enhance the accuracy and relevance of the frame, operational verification was carried out through telephone calls to the listed contacts to confirm their active business status and willingness to participate. This pre-survey verification step is consistent with the best practices in SME research to minimise non-coverage bias and improve data quality.

The initial sample size was estimated to be 291 using Yamane's (1967) formula for finite populations with a 5% margin of error, which is a well-established method in social sciences when the population size is known. To address potential non-response bias, a draft of the questionnaire was pretested with a sample of 30 respondents before the actual administration. The pre-test revealed a 20% non-response rate, necessitating adjustment of the sample size to maintain statistical power and validity. An adjusted sample size of 364 was obtained by dividing the original sample size (291) by the response rate (80%) as recommended by Kish (2005).

With an adjusted sample size of 364, the distribution of the sample across districts was determined in accordance with the proportions of the total FM-SMEs population in the region, as follows: Temeke (146), Ilala (76), Kinondoni (70), Ubungo (54), and Kigamboni (18). This approach was crucial to ensure adequate representation of FM-SMEs in each district, considering that the competitive landscape and accessibility to raw materials may differ across districts. Given the dynamic nature of SMEs, reliance on a single stratification criterion could limit the generalisability of the study. To mitigate this limitation, a second level of stratification was implemented based on enterprise size, categorised as micro, small, and medium enterprises. Categorisation was conducted during data collection based on respondents' disclosure of business characteristics. Of the 350 valid responses used for the analysis, 88 (25.1%) were from micro enterprises, 221 (63.1%) from small enterprises, and 41 (11.7%) from medium enterprises.

Operationalisation and Measurement of Variables

All constructs in the conceptual framework (FM-SMEs performance, CRS, CRC, RWC, and LOY) were treated as latent variables and measured using multiple survey items on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Using multi-item Likert scales enhances reliability and content validity, as having more than one indicator yields a more precise representation of a construct (Sorama & Joensuu-Salo, 2023). A five-point Likert scale is widely used in business research because it is easy for respondents to understand and complete, thereby reducing the chance of confusion or fatigue (Rahmani, 2024; Mumu *et al.*, 2022). Hence, this scale format was deemed appropriate to balance complexity and simplicity, and a preliminary pre-test confirmed that the respondents found this scale easy to understand and use.

Table 1 summarises each construct, including the number of items and literature sources from which the measurement items were adapted. All item wordings were

reviewed and refined after an initial pre-test to ensure that they accurately reflected the operational realities of the FM-SMEs in Tanzania. Feedback from the pre-test indicated that the respondents understood all items clearly; therefore, only minimal rewording was necessary. This process facilitated the improvement of content validity by tailoring language to the local context, without altering the underlying meaning of the constructs.

Table 1: Measurement of Model Variables

Construct	Number of items	Source
CRS	Seven	(Muthuswamy & Al-ameryeen, 2022; Silva & Moreira, 2021)
CRC	Eight	(Hassan <i>et al.</i> , 2022)
RWC	Eight	(Obafemi <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
LOY	Five	(Ismail, 2022; Sampaio <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
FM-SMEs Performance	Twelve	(Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020a; Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020b; Forth & Bryson, 2019)

FM-SMEs performance was measured using five indicators: sales growth, profit growth, employee growth, asset growth, and market share growth. These indicators were chosen because they are widely recognised and commonly used to measure and reflect the multidimensional nature of SMEs performance (Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020a; Kiyabo & Isaga, 2020b; Forth & Bryson, 2019). Given the sensitivity of objective data and reluctance of many SMEs to maintain and disclose financial records, this study opted to use subjective performance measures. Previous studies (Jalali *et al.*, 2020; Duygulu *et al.*, 2016) attested that owners of small businesses are unwilling to disclose the exact financial figures to outsiders. Importantly, there is evidence to support the use of subjective measures because they are reliable and valid indicators of SMEs performance (Vij, 2016).

Data Collection

A cross-sectional survey was conducted among owners or managers of FM-SMEs utilising questionnaires. This approach was chosen because of its ability to gather large amounts of data quickly and cost effectively. Managers/owners were chosen as the focus because they are the primary decision-makers and typically oversee all the operations within their enterprises. Although ethical approval was not required, all the research procedures conformed to the established principles of sound research practice. Participants were briefed on the purpose of the study and assured that their participation was entirely voluntary. It was emphasised that responses would be used exclusively for academic purposes and reported in an aggregate form to maintain anonymity. Before data collection, telephone calls were made to the listed contact numbers to obtain voluntary informed consent.

There was a concern that collecting data on predictor, mediating, and criterion variables from the same respondents using the same questionnaire and ordinal scales could lead to Common Method Bias (CMB). This bias might either exaggerate or diminish the relationships between variables, thus affecting the validity and reliability of the research (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). To address CMB, measurement items from various

sources were incorporated, and questionnaires were administered in person to allow for the immediate clarification of any unclear questions that might cause misinterpretation or careless responses.

To reduce response bias and ensure that the respondents gave honest and careful responses, some precautions were taken. Participants were first assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of the data they supplied. This guarantee was stated in both the survey introduction by trained data collectors, emphasising that individual responses would be held with strict confidence. Second, the performance questions were carefully framed to assess relative performance rather than absolute values. In addition, data collectors were oriented to the research objectives and instructed on how to build rapport with respondents and encourage accurate, reflective responses.

Data Analysis

To assess CBM, Harman's single-factor test was performed using unrotated principal component analysis (PCA) on all measured items. The test examined whether a single factor accounted for less than 50% of the total variance, indicating the absence of CMB (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). Additionally, a Common Latent Factor (CLF) approach was applied to a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) model, where all indicators were loaded onto both their theoretical constructs and a single latent method factor simultaneously. The standardised loadings from the model with CLF were then compared with those from the model without CLF. None of the indicator loadings between the two models changed by more than 0.20 between the two models, suggesting that CMB did not materially influence the results (van der Vaart, 2021). This dual-method evaluation enhances the confidence in the validity of the findings.

After addressing CMB, the suitability of the dataset for factor analysis was assessed. This involved computing the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity to evaluate the presence of correlations among the dataset items. A KMO above 0.5 and close to 1.0, would be considered acceptable, indicating that the data might contain underlying factors (Khairi *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, the significant results in Bartlett's test ($p < 0.05$) would lead to rejection of the null hypothesis of an identity correlation matrix, indicating that the variables were interrelated and suitable for structure detection (Khairi *et al.*, 2021). Given these results, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed to empirically assess and confirm the validity of the measurement items in the context of Tanzanian FM-SMEs.

Although the scales were adapted from prior studies, conducting an EFA was prudent because these instruments had not been previously used in this specific context. All items were subjected to PCA in the EFA. Only factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.0 were extracted, and during the item reduction process, items that exhibited factor loadings above 0.50 on their intended constructs were retained. This is the standard cut-off in factor analysis for practical significance (Jiang *et al.*, 2023). Items that failed to meet this loading threshold were excluded to improve the clarity of the factor structure. This EFA step helped verify that the adapted items clustered into conceptually coherent factors, providing initial confirmation of construct validity before moving to confirmatory analysis.

Further analysis followed a structured approach using Covariance-Based Structural Equation Modelling (CB-SEM) to examine both the measurement and structural models. CB-SEM was preferred over Partial Least Square-SEM (PLS-SEM) because this study focused on theory testing, and the dataset met key assumptions, including a large sample size and normal distribution (Vinkóczy *et al.*, 2024; Hair *et al.*, 2019). Analysis of the measurement models involved conducting CFA using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) version 23 software. AMOS was chosen because of its capability to estimate complex structural relationships, such as mediating effects and path coefficients.

The measurement models were developed based on the results of EFA and were used to confirm whether the data fit the model well and if the latent constructs were reliably and validly measured by their observed indicators. Model fit was assessed using standard indices, including Chi-square statistic (CMIN), Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker–Lewis Index (TLI), Parsimony-adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (PGFI), Residual Mean Square (RMR), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), applying recommended cut-off values. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), with recommended thresholds of 0.7 and 0.6 respectively (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

The construct validity was tested using convergent and discriminant (divergent) validity. Convergent validity was assessed using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with a recommended threshold of 0.50 or higher (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Discriminant validity was assessed using the heterotrait–monotrait (HTMT) ratio, with values below 0.85 considered evidence of adequate discriminant validity (Henseler *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, the key assumption requirements of the structural equation model, such as linearity, multivariate normality, and multicollinearity, were assessed to ensure that the data were suitable for subsequent analyses.

After validating the measurement models through CFA, analysis of the structural models was conducted to specify and test the hypothesised direct and indirect paths among the latent constructs. To examine the significance of the mediating effect of LOY on the link between collaborative network dimensions and FM-SMEs performance indirect effects, a bootstrapping technique was applied with 5,000 resamples at a 95% confidence interval. This large number of resamples increases the stability and reliability of the confidence interval for the mediated effect (Preacher & Hayes, 2008).

Results and Discussion

Response Rate

A total of 364 questionnaires were distributed, all of which were returned, resulting in an initial response rate of 100 %. Following data screening, 14 were discarded owing to incomplete responses, yielding a final sample size of 350 out of 364. Thus, the valid response rate, calculated as the number of complete surveys divided by the distributed surveys, was 96%.

Common Method Bias Analysis

Harman’s one-factor test indicated that neither the initial unrotated factor nor the first rotated factor exceeded the conservative 50 % variance threshold for CMB. Our findings revealed that the first component of the unrotated factor explained 31.55 % of the total variance, and in the case of the rotated factor, it explained approximately 15.58 %. The overall cumulative percentage of the variance explained by the rotation sum of the squared loadings was 64.18 %. To further assess the CMB, the CLF method was applied by estimating a model with and without CLF and then comparing the standardized path coefficients between the two models. Differences remained under the 0.20 cut-off recommended by Podsakoff *et al.* (2003), confirming that CMB did not materially bias the structural estimates. These results indicate the absence of a dominant method factor.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

The appropriateness of the dataset for factor analysis was confirmed through EFA using PCA with Varimax rotation. The KMO measure indicated excellent sampling adequacy (KMO = 0.939), whereas Bartlett’s test of sphericity was highly significant ($\chi^2 = 8570.445$, $p < 0.001$), thus rejecting the null hypothesis of an identity correlation matrix. Moreover, a small determinant (5.676×10^{-12}), indicating multicollinearity, and the varimax-rotated component matrix displayed a simple structure with clear factor loadings across the distinct components. Table 2 presents the rotated component matrix with factor loadings for all the items. Items loaded clearly on their respective components, with values exceeding the 0.50 threshold, confirming their practical significance.

Table 2: Rotated Component Matrix Indicating Items’ Factor Loadings

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
FP6	0.768					
FP4	0.724					
FP5	0.713					
FP7	0.684					
FP1	0.680					
FP9	0.678					
FP2	0.667					
FP8	0.657					
FP10	0.651					
FP3	0.647					
CRS2		0.808				
CRS1		0.791				
CRS6		0.788				
CRS5		0.776				
CRS4		0.752				
CRS3		0.745				
CRS7		0.745				
RWC8			0.798			
RWC3			0.796			

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
RWC4			0.780			
RWC2			0.759			
RWC7			0.759			
RWC5			0.756			
RWC1			0.734			
CRC8			0.537			
RWC6			0.525			
CRC3				0.858		
CRC4				0.788		
CRC7				0.774		
CRC1				0.761		
CRC2				0.727		
CRC6				0.697		
CRC5				0.581		
LOY3					0.719	
LOY1					0.698	
LOY4					0.661	
LOY2					0.660	
LOY5					0.592	
FP11						-0.777
FP12						0.333
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.						
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.						

Following Varimax rotation, six components were extracted. In line with the recommendation that items with factor loadings below 0.5 and factors with fewer than three items should be excluded to ensure convergent validity and factor stability (Arifin & Yusoff, 2016), some adjustments were necessary. Notably, the sixth component was found to consist of only two items (FP11 and FP12). FP11 exhibited a strong but negative loading (-0.777), whereas FP12 was weakly loaded (0.333). The negative loading of FP11 indicates an inverse association with the latent construct, which in this case did not align conceptually with the other FP items. Thus, the sixth component did not meaningfully contribute to the measurement of the intended construct, and was therefore excluded from further analysis. Similarly, one item (CRC8) overlapped with items forming another construct (RWC) and hence was dropped. Taken together, a total of three items were removed during the EFA, leading to a final five-factor structure consisting of 37 items. This identification of problematic items justified conducting EFA instead of directly applying CFA, ultimately enhancing the validity of the measurement and structural models across different populations and contexts (Tavakol & Wetzel, 2020).

Reliability and Validity Analysis

As shown in Table 3, all constructs exhibited strong reliability, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeding the threshold of 0.7 and CR values surpassing the minimum threshold of 0.60 as recommended by Fornell and Larcker (1981). Regarding convergent validity, three constructs (CRC, CRS, and RWC) met the AVE threshold of 0.50. Although the AVE values for FM-SMEs performance (0.479) and LOY (0.451) fell slightly below the conventional 0.50 threshold, their CR values were greater than 0.60, and all standardized factor loadings exceeded 0.50, indicating adequate convergent validity (Juanamasta *et al.*, 2023; Maruf *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the model fit indices for both the measurement and structural models confirmed that the overall model was acceptable and stable.

Table 3: Reliability and Validity Test for Study Constructs

Construct	No. of items	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
FM-SME Performance	10	0.918	0.902	0.479
LOY	5	0.872	0.803	0.451
CRC	7	0.896	0.896	0.555
CRS	7	0.921	0.912	0.597
RWC	8	0.893	0.909	0.558

Table 4 reports the HTMT ratios for the constructs. All inter-construct HTMT values were below the threshold of 0.85, confirming that the constructs were empirically distinct (Henseler *et al.*, 2015). This finding supports discriminant validity, indicating that each latent variable measures a unique conceptual dimension within the study framework.

Table 4: Assessment of Divergent Validity Using HTMT

Construct	FM-SMEs Performance	CRC	CRS	RWC
CRC	0.4904			
CRS	0.6347	0.5438		
RWC	0.3090	0.1629	0.3109	
LOY	0.7803	0.4224	0.6554	0.3135

Confirming the Measurement Models for the Study Constructs

The CFA results revealed a satisfactory model fit across all the constructs. Although some chi-square values were significant (as expected in large samples), the chi-square/degrees of freedom ratios for all the models were below the recommended threshold of 3. For instance, CRC ($\chi^2/df = 3.636/14 = 0.2597$), CRS ($27.791/13 = 2.14$), and LOY ($13.937/5 = 2.79$) all indicated a good model fit. Fit indices further supported model adequacy, with CFI ranging from 0.983 to 0.996 and TLI between 0.973 and 0.994, both exceeding the 0.90 threshold. The RMSEA values ranged from 0.028 to 0.072. Values below 0.05 indicate a close fit, and those between 0.05 and 0.08 indicate a reasonable fit (Kline, 2023). Thus, all constructs exhibited an acceptable to close fit.

Assumptions of the SEM

Before conducting the SEM analysis, key assumptions were assessed and satisfied, including multivariate normality evidenced by skewness values between -3 and +3 and kurtosis within -10 to +10 (Brown, 2015), linearity confirmed through scatterplot analysis, and absence of multicollinearity indicated by Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values below 10 and tolerance levels above 0.1 (Hair *et al.*, 2019). Table 5 presents the summary statistics for the model. The R-squared value of 0.553 indicates that CRS, CRC, RWC, and LOY collectively explain 55.3% of the variance in the FM-SMEs performance. This represents substantial explanatory power in behavioural research, highlighting the importance of collaborative networks and customer loyalty in predicting firm performance.

Table 5: Model Summary Statistics on R-Squared Values

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.743 ^a	0.553	0.547	0.4425
a. Predictors: (Constant), LOY, CRC, CRS and RWC while the dependent variable is FM-SME performance				

Hypotheses Testing

Analysis of direct effects in path models

Two structural equation models were specified to test the hypothesised relationships: one excluding the mediator and the other incorporating it, as depicted in Figures 2(a) and 2(b). The Chi-square/degree of freedom ratios $736.279/452 = 1.628$ and $994.168/613 = 1.621$ were below the threshold of < 3 , indicating well-fitting models (Kline, 2023). For the model without the mediator, the fit indices were CFI = 0.959, TLI = 0.955, RFI = 0.890, RMSEA = 0.042, and SRMR = 0.0516. For the model with mediator, the indices were CFI = 0.953, TLI = 0.948, RFI = 0.876, RMSEA = 0.042, and SRMR = 0.0523. Although the RFI values (0.890 and 0.876) were slightly below the cut-off of 0.90, these results remained acceptable, especially when dealing with complex models comprising multiple latent constructs (Ramírez *et al.*, 2025). All other indices met the recommended criteria (CFI and TLI > 0.95 ; RMSEA < 0.05 ; SRMR < 0.08), thereby confirming that both models achieved adequate and theoretically defensible fit. Table 6 summarises the path coefficients for the direct effects before and after including LOY as a mediator.

In the baseline model, all three dimensions of collaborative networks had statistically significant and positive direct effects on FM-SME performance before inclusion of the mediator. However, the magnitude of influence varied across the dimensions of collaborative networks. Notably, CRS exhibited the strongest effect ($\beta = 0.501$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that partnerships with suppliers substantially enhance firm performance. Collaboration with suppliers is likely to facilitate reliable inputs, operational efficiency, and co-innovation, all of which contribute to competitive advantage (Stekelorum *et al.*, 2022). This finding is consistent with previous studies emphasising the role of supplier-focused collaboration and supply chain integration in

improving SMEs performance (Israel, 2025; Uwamahoro *et al.*, 2024; Mulyana & Wasitowati, 2021).

Figure 2. (a) Structural Model without Mediator

Figure 2. (b) Structural Model with Mediator

CRC also exhibited a significant positive influence ($\beta = 0.182, p = 0.002$), implying that competitive arrangements can support performance by allowing firms to share resources, engage in joint learning, and expand market access. This finding supports the view that network ties with industry peers contribute to firm success and echoes the finding that a competitive mindset positively influences SME performance (Worimegbe et al., 2022). Although comparatively weaker, RWC had a statistically significant effect as well ($\beta = 0.116, p = 0.019$), suggesting that firms that proactively engage with customers are better positioned to align their offerings with market demand, thereby strengthening their competitive position. This finding supports prior studies indicating that customer-centric strategies improve responsiveness and satisfaction (Ismail, 2023; Obafemi et al., 2023). These significant baseline effects satisfied the first condition for mediation analysis, as per Baron and Kenny (1986), thereby justifying further examination of indirect pathways through the inclusion of LOY as a mediating construct.

Table 6: Analysis of Direct Effects

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	<i>p</i>
A: Excluding the Mediator							
FM-SME performance	<--	CRS	0.340	0.501	0.043	7.916	***
FM-SME performance	<--	CRC	0.148	0.182	0.047	3.172	0.002
FM-SME performance	<--	RWC	0.129	0.116	0.055	2.337	0.019
B: Including the Mediator							
H ₈ : LOY	<--	RWC	0.139	0.116	0.061	2.265	0.023
H ₂ : LOY	<--	CRS	0.425	0.584	0.050	8.564	***
H ₅ : LOY	<--	CRC	0.054	0.062	0.025	1.264	0.033
H ₄ : FM-SME performance	<--	CRC	0.117	0.142	0.041	2.883	0.004
H ₁₀ : FM-SME performance	<--	LOY	0.582	0.617	0.067	8.692	***
H ₇ : FM-SME performance	<--	RWC	0.049	0.044	0.048	1.018	0.309
H ₁ : FM-SME performance	<--	CRS	0.099	0.144	0.042	2.367	0.018

The inclusion of LOY in the structural model revealed notable changes in the direct effects of the collaborative network dimensions on performance. The direct effect of CRS on performance diminished, but remained significant ($\beta = 0.144, p = 0.018$), indicating the potential for partial mediation. Similarly, the direct effect of CRC on performance reduced but remained significant ($\beta = 0.142, p = 0.004$), also fulfilling the partial mediation condition, as recommended by Baron and Kenny (1986).

In contrast, RWC turned to a nonsignificant direct effect on FM-SMEs performance ($\beta = 0.044, p = 0.309$) despite its significant association with LOY ($\beta = 0.116, p = 0.023$).

This pattern suggests full mediation, in line with Baron and Kenny's (1986) framework, which posits that full mediation occurs when a previously significant direct effect becomes nonsignificant upon the inclusion of a mediating variable. In this context, customer engagement strategies alone may not directly improve firm performance unless they translate into stronger LOY. Thus, the influence of RWC on FM-SMEs performance is contingent on the firm's ability to go beyond transactional engagement, and instead focuses on consistent value delivery, service reliability, and customer-centric innovation.

This finding aligns with the RMT (Morgan & Hunt, 1994), which emphasises loyalty as the key mechanism through which relational efforts yield economic benefits. For example, Sampaio et al. (2020) and Ismail (2023) found that customer-oriented strategies contribute to firm performance primarily through loyalty. These studies suggest that, while customer engagement can improve satisfaction and relational bonds, loyalty ultimately drives the critical elements of SMEs performance. Moreover, in markets characterised by price sensitivity or commoditised offerings, as is often the case for FM-SMEs, functional values, such as product quality, reliability, and pricing, may outweigh emotional or relational factors.

Among the predictors of LOY, CRS had the strongest positive effect ($\beta = 0.584$, $p < 0.001$), reinforcing the idea that strategic supplier partnerships contribute to LOY. This finding is supported by network theory (Granovetter, 1985; Burt, 1992), which posits that firms derive competitive advantage not only from internal capabilities but also from the strength of their inter-organisational ties. Reliable and high-quality supplier relationships enhance consistency in product or service delivery, which in turn strengthens customer trust and loyalty. In contexts such as FM-SMEs, where customer expectations are heavily influenced by operational reliability and value assurance, effective supplier collaboration becomes a critical upstream determinant of customer experience and loyalty.

Although CRC had the weakest effect ($\beta = 0.062$, $p = 0.033$), it still made a statistically significant contribution to LOY. This may be explained by the benefits of cooperation, where collaboration among peer firms leads to shared innovation, improved service standards, and collective learning. Such joint initiatives can indirectly enhance customer perceptions of value and professionalism, thereby increasing loyalty. Prior studies, such as those by Crick (2022), have shown that cooperation arrangements can enhance LOY when managed carefully. In the context of FM-SMEs, competitor collaborations that expand service options or stabilize market quality can signal credibility and increase customer attachment.

Surprisingly, RWC, despite being traditionally viewed as a cornerstone of loyalty-building, had only a modest effect on LOY ($\beta = 0.116$, $p = 0.023$). This suggests that in this particular business context, customer engagement strategies may not strongly translate into loyalty unless supported by more functional or value-driven factors. One plausible explanation is that relational engagement, while relationship-building efforts are important, may not be sufficient to generate LOY unless complemented by tangible attributes, such as product quality, reliability, or service excellence.

LOY exhibited a strong and statistically significant direct effect on FM-SMEs performance ($\beta = 0.617$, $p < 0.001$), highlighting its critical role in translating

collaborative strategies into performance gains. These findings are in line with the RMT, which identifies LOY as a key driver of firm performance in competitive environments. These findings are also consistent with empirical studies by Sampaio et al. (2020) and Ismail (2023), who found that loyalty mediates the relationship between strategic orientations and SMEs performance across sectors and geographic contexts.

The hypotheses of the study were evaluated based on the results of the full structural model, which included LOY as a mediating variable. The findings supported H1, which suggests that CRS positively influences FM-SMEs performance, and H4, which posits that CRC has a positive effect on FM-SMEs performance. H7, which hypothesised a direct effect of RWC on FM-SMEs performance, was not supported in the mediated model as the relationship became statistically non-significant. H10 was confirmed, as LOY had a strong positive effect on FM-SMEs performance. H2, H5 and H8 were supported, indicating that CRS, CRC, and RWC significantly influenced LOY.

Overall, the findings highlight the multifaceted influence of collaborative network dimensions on FM-SMEs performance, as revealed by their direct effects in the full structural model. Among the three dimensions, CRS emerged as the strongest predictor of both LOY and FM-SMEs performance. CRC also showed statistically significant direct effects on LO- and FM-SMEs performance. Although RWC was significantly associated with LOY, its direct effect on FM-SMEs performance was not statistically significant after including LOY, implying that customer engagement influences performance primarily through loyalty rather than through a direct route. The results affirm that LOY serves as a critical conduit through which collaborative strategies, particularly those involving suppliers and competitors, are translated into enhanced firm performance while also emphasising that customer engagement must be reinforced by value-adding mechanisms to yield substantial performance.

Analysis of the Mediating Effect Using Bootstrapping Methods

Before conducting the mediation analysis, measurement invariance across micro, small, and medium firms was assessed using a multi-group CFA. Configural invariance was established ($CMIN/df = 1.385$), and metric invariance was confirmed as the chi-square difference test was not significant ($\Delta\chi^2 = 38.674$, $p = 0.753$). The fit indices (TLI and $CFI > 0.90$; $RMR < 0.08$) indicated that the factor structure and loadings were equivalent across the groups, justifying the pooled analysis. With the invariance established, bootstrapped mediation analysis was conducted using CB-SEM to generate bias-corrected estimates of indirect effects, thereby enhancing the precision and validity of the results. The mediating role LOY on the pathways from RWC, CRC, and CRS on FM-SMEs performance is presented in Tables 7–9.

As shown in Table 7, the R-squared value of 0.3712 indicates that CRC, RWC, and CRS jointly explained 37.12% of the variance in LOY, highlighting their relevance as key predictors. All predictors exhibited significant positive effects on LOY, with 95% confidence intervals excluding zero at the 5% significance level. CRS had the strongest standardized effect ($\beta = 0.4377$), followed by RWC ($\beta = 0.1457$) and CRC ($\beta = 0.0842$), confirming their contribution to loyalty enhancement.

Table 7: Effects of RWC, CRC, and CRS on LOY

A: Model Summary						
R	R-squared	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
0.6092	0.3712	0.4207	68.0768	3.0000	346.0000	0.0000
B: Model parameter estimates						
	Coeff.	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.1755	0.2425	4.8470	0.0000	0.6985	1.6525
RWC	0.1457	0.0549	2.6532	0.0083	0.0377	0.2537
CRC	0.0842	0.0393	2.1397	0.0331	0.0068	0.1615
CRS	0.4377	0.0437	10.0163	0.0000	0.3518	0.5237

The analysis presented in Table 8 indicates that predictors, along with LOY, explained 55.2% of the variance in FM-SMEs performance, indicating a strong explanatory model. LOY emerged as the most influential variable ($\beta = 0.4096$, $p < 0.001$), reaffirming its central role as a key driver of performance. CRS maintained a significant effect ($\beta = 0.1406$, $p < 0.001$), followed by CRC ($\beta = 0.0905$, $p = 0.0009$). Conversely, RWC showed a positive but statistically insignificant effect on performance ($\beta = 0.0671$, $p = 0.0771$), suggesting that its influence may be indirect or contextually contingent.

Table 8: Direct Effects of RWC, CRC, and CRS on FM-SMEs Performance, Accounting for LOY

A: Model Summary						
R	R-squared	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
0.7432	0.5524	0.1958	106.4409	4.0000	345.0000	0.0000
B: Model Parameter Estimates						
	Coeff.	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.1118	0.1710	6.5015	0.0000	0.7755	1.4481
RWC	0.0671	0.0378	1.7730	0.0771	-0.0073	0.1415
LOY	0.4096	0.0367	11.1654	0.0000	0.3374	0.4817
CRC	0.0905	0.0270	3.3506	0.0009	0.0374	0.1437
CRS	0.1406	0.0339	4.1530	0.0000	0.0740	0.2073

Bootstrapping was used to estimate the indirect effects of CRC, RWC, and CRS on FM-SMEs performance through LOY, thus providing a robust non-parametric method for mediation analysis. Table 9 presents the mediation results with bias-corrected confidence intervals, where significance is indicated if the intervals exclude zero. This approach enhances accuracy and statistical power in detecting mediation effects, confirming LOY's role as a mediator.

Table 9: Indirect Effects of ISS, SES, and CRS on FM-SMEs Performance, Accounting for LOY

Path	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
H ₉ : FM-SMEs Performance < --- LOY < ---RWC	0.0597	0.0250	0.0108	0.1096
H ₆ : FM-SMEs Performance < --- LOY < ---CRC	0.0345	0.0175	0.0023	0.0707
H ₃ : FM-SMEs Performance < --- LOY < ---CRS	0.1793	0.0265	0.1282	0.2332

Note: Bootstrap resampling = 5,000 at the 95% level.

The mediating effect of LOY on the relationship between collaborative network dimensions and the performance of FM-SMEs was assessed using path coefficients and corresponding confidence intervals. For RWC, a statistically significant positive effect on LOY was observed ($\beta = 0.1457$; 95% CI: 0.0377, 0.2537), alongside a direct insignificant positive effect on FM-SMEs Performance even after controlling for LOY ($\beta = 0.0671$; 95% CI: -0.0073, 0.1415). The indirect effect of RWC on FM-SMEs performance via LOY was also significant ($\beta = 0.0597$; 95% CI: 0.00108–0.1096), indicating that LOY fully mediated the effects of RWC on FM-SMEs performance.

Similarly, CRS exhibited a strong positive effect on LOY ($\beta = 0.4377$; 95% CI: 0.3518, 0.5237) and maintained a significant direct effect on FM-SMEs Performance after accounting for LOY ($\beta = 0.1406$; 95% CI: 0.0740, 0.2073). CRC showed a significant positive effect on LOY ($\beta = 0.0842$; 95% CI: 0.068, 0.1615), and a statistically significant direct effect on FM-SMEs performance ($\beta = 0.1406$; 95% CI: 0.0740, 0.2073) when controlling for LOY, CRS, and RWC. Moreover, the indirect effect of CRC ($\beta = 0.0345$; 95% CI: 0.0023, 0.0707) and CRS ($\beta = 0.1793$; 95% CI: 0.0128, 0.2332) on LOY was significant, suggesting that LOY partially mediated the effect of CRC and CRS on FM-SMEs performance.

Overall, the analysis of the direct and indirect paths highlights the significant influence of collaborative network dimensions on FM-SMEs performance via LOY. These findings affirm LOY's position as a mediator in relating collaborative network dimensions and firm performance, thereby supporting H3, H6, and H9. LOY serves as a partial mediator of CRS, CRC, and FM-SMEs performance.

Discussion

The findings of this study provide important insights into how collaborative networks influence the performance of FM-SMEs, with LOY serving as the critical mediating mechanism. The results affirm the centrality of collaborative strategies in resource-constrained environments, consistent with the propositions of Network Theory, which emphasises that firm success is embedded in inter-organisational ties (Granovetter, 1985; Burt, 1992).

CRS emerged as the strongest predictor of both LOY and firm performance, highlighting the strategic value of supplier partnerships in ensuring reliable inputs, enhancing operational efficiency, and sustaining consistent product quality, all of which translate into improved customer trust and loyalty. The finding aligns with Liu *et al.* (2024) and Uwamahoro *et al.* (2024), who observed that supplier-focused collaborations improve SMEs' performance by strengthening supply chain reliability and fostering innovation. Within the Tanzanian FM-SMEs context, where customers often prioritise value, durability, and affordability, effective supplier relationships serve as an upstream determinant of LO and subsequent firm success.

CRC also demonstrated significant direct and indirect effects on performance, confirming the relevance of cooperation in this sector. While competitor collaboration has been described as a “double-edged sword” (Bimmermann *et al.*, 2024), this study found that when carefully managed, such relationships can expand market opportunities, enable

joint procurement, and foster shared learning that indirectly enhances loyalty. This finding is consistent with Crick (2022), who established that cooperative ties among SMEs improve market outcomes and customer satisfaction. The findings suggest that cooperation can strengthen both functional and relational outcomes, provided that competitive tensions do not undermine trust and coordination.

Interestingly, RWC, which is often considered the cornerstone of market orientation, did not show a significant direct effect on performance once LOY was accounted for. Instead, the effect of RWC on performance was fully mediated by loyalty, suggesting that relational engagement must be converted into tangible loyalty to yield superior performance. This result supports the tenets of RMT (Berry, 1983; Morgan & Hunt, 1994), which posits that the true economic value of customer relationships is realised through loyalty rather than mere engagement. It also echoes the findings of Ismail (2023), who showed that customer orientation influences SMEs performance, primarily through loyalty-building mechanisms.

Taken together, these findings advance the literature on SMEs by reframing collaborative networks as not only structural mechanisms for overcoming resource limitations, but also as relational strategies that drive loyalty. They extend the traditional market orientation framework by positioning collaborative networks as substitutes for inter-functional coordination, which is often less relevant for SMEs because of their informality and limited internal resources (Mamman, 2021).

Most importantly, the study highlights that LOY is not simply a by-product of customer engagement but the central conduit through which all collaborative efforts, whether with suppliers, competitors, or customers, are transformed into performance gains. In price-sensitive and quality-driven markets, such as Tanzania, loyalty is built not only through personal rapport but also through consistent product quality, timely delivery, and value-for-money offerings. This insight highlights the necessity of aligning relational strategies with operational excellence to ensure sustainable competitive advantage.

Conclusion, Implications and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study concludes that collaborative networks are paramount in enhancing FM-SMEs performance in Tanzania through LOY as a mediator. Grounded in Network and Relationship Marketing theories, the findings reveal that the impact of firm's collaboration with suppliers and competitors on FM-SMEs performance is partially mediated by LOY, while the influence of RWC is fully mediated. CRS and CRC emerged as the most impactful, reinforcing the strategic value of collaboration with suppliers and competitors in resource-constrained settings. Empirically, the study challenges the conventional view that customer engagement alone drives performance, revealing instead that in price-sensitive and quality-driven markets, loyalty must be earned through consistent value delivery and strategic external linkages. The study reframes collaborative networks as supportive strategies to the essential pillars of SMEs competitiveness, calling for a rethinking of SMEs growth models to prioritise loyalty-driven, network-enabled performance pathways.

Theoretical implication

This study extends the traditional market orientation framework by introducing collaborative networks as a substitute for inter-functional coordination in the context of SMEs. It also broadens RMT by revealing that loyalty is not only the outcome of customer–firm ties but also the relational payoff of wider external collaborations. Contextualised in Tanzanian FM-SMEs, this study adapts these theories to developing economies where performance depends on loyalty-driven, network-enabled strategies. By integrating Network Theory and RMT, this study highlights LOY as a key mechanism that links collaborative networks to firm performance.

Practical implications for FM-SMEs

The findings provide actionable insights for FM-SMEs by establishing that strategic collaborations, particularly with suppliers and competitors, significantly boost performance through LOY. However, to translate RWC into loyalty and improved performance, firms must complement relationship-building with tangible value delivery, such as reliable products and responsive services.

Policy implications

This study justifies the need for policy interventions to promote and support interfirm networking among SMEs. By enabling collaborative mechanisms, policymakers can help address resource constraints, improve competitiveness, and foster innovation among informal and resource-limited enterprises, such as FM-SMEs.

Recommendations

FM-SMEs should build long-term collaborative relationships with suppliers and competitors to improve access to quality inputs, reduce procurement costs, drive innovation, and expand their market reach. This can be achieved through alliances for joint procurement of materials, organising knowledge/skills exchange forums, sharing specialised machinery with trusted competitors to enhance, and forming joint marketing consortia to exhibit at major trade fairs under one banner. Further, beyond relational engagement with customers, FM-SMEs should ensure consistent product quality, timely delivery, and responsive after-sales services to build long-term customer trust and repeat business.

The Ministry of Industry and Trade, should support inter-firm networking by promoting clustering programs, shared resource centres, and supplier development initiatives. In collaboration with local authorities and SIDO, the Ministry should facilitate peer learning forums, trade fairs, and supplier-buyer linkages. Additionally, incentives such as simplified tax procedures, collective branding support, and preferential access to public procurement should be introduced to enhance FM-SMEs competitiveness.

Limitations and Areas for Further Study

This study had some limitations which offer directions for future research. First, the exclusive use of a quantitative approach limits insight into the underlying dynamics of collaborative networks and LOY. Future research should incorporate qualitative data to gain more insight. Second, moderating factors, such as firm size, age, and industry turbulence, were not examined. Future studies should examine moderation effects to understand how these factors shape the collaborative network–performance relationship. Third, the reliance on self-reported data from owners and managers may introduce bias, even though steps were taken to mitigate common method variance. Future studies should triangulate data using customer feedback or incorporate objective performance metrics where feasible. Fourth, while this study focused on supplier, competitor, and customer relationships, other potential network dimensions, such as relationships with regulators, NGOs, and financial institutions, were not examined. Investigating these additional actors could provide a more comprehensive view of how external collaborations influence SME performance. Finally, future research could explore the moderating effects of firm size, digital adoption, and industry turbulence on the relationship among collaborative networks, loyalty, and performance.

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This manuscript was partially written with the help of OpenAI ChatGPT-4 for language enhancement, grammar correction, and formatting. The authors reviewed and revised all the AI-generated content to ensure accuracy and alignment with the research objectives. The test for Harman’s single-factor that was undertaken revealed that both the first unrotated and rotated factors, which present the largest variability in the original dataset were below the 50% threshold endorsed by Podsakoff *et al.* (2003). Specifically, the first factor which was not rotated accounted for 39.2%, while the rotated first factor counted 16.2% of the total variance. The results suggest that CBM was unlikely to significantly distort the observed relationships among the constructs. Further validation using the CLF approach indicated that the differences between standardized regression weights for each of the observed variables in the models with and without the CLF were minimally below 0.2. Since all differences remained below the recommended cut-off of 0.20, these findings reinforce the conclusion that CMB was not a solemn issue of interest in this research.

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Appendix I: Computation of Sample Size for the Study

Step 1: Initial Sample Size Calculation

The initial sample size was calculated using Yamane's formula for finite populations, as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = 1,062 (total number of FM-SMEs in Dar es Salaam)

e = 0.05 (5% margin of error)

Substituting these values into the formula yields:

$$n = \frac{1,062}{1 + 1062(0.05)^2} \approx 291$$

Step 2: Adjusting for non-responses

Before the actual data collection, a pre-test was conducted with 30 respondents, and a non-response rate of 20% was observed. To adjust for this nonresponse rate, the sample size was increased.

The adjusted sample size was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Adjusted Sample Size} = \frac{n}{1 - \text{Non response Rate}}$$

Where the non-response rate was 20% or 0.20. Thus, the calculation becomes:

$$\text{Adjusted Sample Size} = \frac{291}{1 - 0.2} \approx 364$$

Step 3: Proportionate Stratified Sampling

Proportionate stratified random sampling was used to ensure representation from each district. The sample size for each district was calculated based on the proportion of the total population of the FM-SMEs. The proportions were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Ilala} = \frac{223}{1,060} \times 364 \approx 76$$

$$\text{Temeke} = \frac{427}{1,060} \times 364 \approx 146$$

$$\text{Kigamboni} = \frac{53}{1,060} \times 364 \approx 18$$

$$\text{Ubungo} = \frac{156}{1,060} \times 364 \approx 54$$

$$\text{Kinondoni} = \frac{203}{1,060} \times 364 \approx 70$$

Appendix II: Description of Study Constructs with Corresponding Observable Items

Variable	Code	Measurement Items
FM-SMEs Performance	FP1	Sales have shown consistent growth over the past 5 years, meeting our expectations
	FP2	Sales growth has been on par with our competitors over the past 5 years
	FP3	We have demonstrated good ability to overcome challenges and obstacles to achieve sales growth
	FP4	Workforce has increased over the past 5 years
	FP5	Growth in number of employees has been in line with competitors over the past 5 years
	FP6	Profitability has noticeably increased over the past 5 years
	FP7	We have experienced an increase in market share over the past five years
	FP8	Our Return on Assets (ROA) has remained stable, indicating asset growth
	FP9	Our enterprise has experienced increase in asset value over the past five years
	FP10	Our enterprise has effectively utilized financial resources to expand its operations
	FP11	We have diversified our asset portfolio to maximize growth
	FP12	Our strategic initiatives have yielded significant profit growth
Corroborative Relationships with Suppliers	CRS1	We view suppliers as strategic partners rather than just vendors
	CSR2	We participate in training programmes offered by our suppliers on new materials and technologies
	CSR3	We involve suppliers at early stage of the product development process to foster innovation
	CSR4	We work with suppliers to explore innovative opportunities and new markets
	CSR5	We value and act on feedback from our suppliers to strengthen our partnerships
	CSR6	We are committed to resolving conflicts with suppliers amicably
	CSR7	We consistently engage with our suppliers to address and resolve material quality concerns
Collaborative Relationship with Coopetitors (CRC)	CRC1	We regularly share market information with other furniture SMEs to improve our operations

	CRC2	We sometimes collaborate with competitors on large orders or shared contracts
	CRC3	We engage in mutual referrals or recommend customers to other furniture SMEs when necessary.
	CRC4	We participate in joint exhibitions, events, or trade fairs with other furniture SMEs.
	CRC5	We learn from our competitors by exchanging ideas or best practices in an open and constructive manner
	CRC6	We jointly discuss challenges affecting our industry with other furniture SMEs
	CRC7	We partner with competing firms to jointly purchase raw materials at better prices
	CRC8	We are part of a local business association or informal group of furniture makers that shares opportunities
	Relationship with Customers	RWC1
RWC2		We frequently seek feedback from customers to improve our products and services
RWC3		We maintain close and long-term relationships with key customers.
RWC4		We regularly communicate with our customers to understand their evolving preferences
RWC5		We treat customers as partners by integrating their suggestions into our design and production processes
RWC6		We encourage customers to share ideas for new furniture styles or functionalities
RWC7		We offer personalized after-sales support to strengthen our customer relationships
RWC8		We adjust our marketing and communication strategies based on direct customer feedback.
Customer Loyalty (LOY)	LOY1	Our customers often return to make repeat purchases
	LOY2	We regularly receive new customers referred by existing customers
	LOY3	We regularly receive positive feedback from repeat customers
	LOY4	Our customers are more forgiving of occasional mistakes or issues
	LOY5	Our customers are willing to pay premium price for our furniture

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